

Kinetics and Mechanisms of the Acid-Catalyzed Dissociation of *Trans*-Dicyanobisbiguanidecobalt(III) Chloride

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Investigations were carried out on the acid-catalyzed dissociation of *trans*-dicyanobisbiguanidecobalt(III) ion in presence of 0.1-0.5M perchloric acid in the temperature range 28°- 40°. In this range, only one 'biguanide' dissociates from the complex ion with the formation of (*cis*) diaquodicyanomonobiguanidecobalt(III) ion. Activation parameters were evaluated in the usual way ($\Delta H^\ddagger = 15.6 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$; $\Delta S^\ddagger = -24 \text{ e.u.}$) and these values indicate that the mechanism of dissociation is similar to other cobalt-biguanide complexes. Bond-breaking in the transition state is more important than other factors.

NUMEROUS studies on the kinetics of the dissociation of bidentate chelates from cobalt(III) complexes are available in literature¹⁻⁵. Protonation mechanism has been suggested for the acid-catalyzed dissociation of these flexible bidentate basic ligands⁶. In presence of acidic aqueous solution, biguanide complexes of cobalt(III), form protonated intermediates (conjugate acids)¹. The presence of a non-labile inert ligand may have an influence on the formation of the conjugate acid and thus on the rate. In order to study the effect of such ligands, present work was undertaken to investigate the influence of cyanide on the dissociation of the biguanide in *trans*-dicyanobisbiguanidecobalt(III) ion. In acid solution, this complex ion release biguanides in stages, the conditions being wide apart in acidity and temperature and in present investigation only the first step of dissociation with the formation of *trans*-dicyano (*cis*) diaquomonobiguanidecobalt(III) ion is reported. Along with this complex ion, an attempt was made to study the dissociation of the similar complex ion *trans*-dicyanobisethylenediaminecobalt(III) ion and all these are reported in the following pages.

Experimental

Reagents :

Trans-Dicyano-bis-biguanidecobalt(III) chloride was prepared of the method of Sengupta and Ray⁷. It was recrystallized from the aqueous solution and was used for kinetic studies. Found : Co-17.32 ; N-47.96 percent. Calculated for $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_7)_2(\text{CN})_2] \text{Cl}$: Co-17.00 ; N-48.29 percent.

Trans-Dicyano-bis-ethylenediaminecobalt(III) chloride. The corresponding sulphate was prepared by

the method of Ray and Sharma⁸ and its purity was checked by analysis Found : N-26.95 and Co-9.41 ; Calculated for $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_8\text{N}_2)_2(\text{CN})_2]_2 \text{SO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and N-27.45 Co-9.64. The perchlorate salt was prepared in solution before use by the metathesis of an equivalent amount of complex sulphate with barium perchlorate in solution. Stock solutions of perchloric acid were prepared using reagent grade (G.R.E Merck) acid and were standardized as usual.

Sodium perchlorate (fluka) was twice recrystallized from water and dried at 150° before use.

All other chemicals used were of reagent grade or else were purified by suitable methods. Distilled water redistilled with a little amount of alkali and potassium permanganate in an all glass still was used for making the solutions.

Apparatus and procedure : A Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurements. Spectra of the solutions of $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ complex ion with different acid concentrations from 0.01-2M perchloric acid were recorded immediately after preparation and also after 1, 2, 3 hours ; 1, 2, etc. upto 10 days keeping the solutions at room temperature. There was an initial change in the absorption spectra of all the solutions. The absorption spectra in the acid range 0.05-2.0 M for the biguanide complex remains almost unchanged after 2-3 days. At this stage only one 'biguanide' dissociates from the experimental complex with the formation of $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})\text{H}_2\text{O}]_2(\text{CN})_2^+$ and represents the absorbance for diaquo complex which was actually isolated from the solution. Figure 1 records the spectra of 0.0005 M aqueous solution of the experimental, and the product diaquodicyano-mono-biguanidecobalt(III), complex ions. At 80°, spectra of the solutions

Fig.1. Absorption spectra of 0.0005 M aqueous solutions of (a) *trans*-dicyanobisbiguanidecobalt(III) ion and (b) *trans*-dicyanocis-diaquomonobiguanidecobalt(III) ion (absorbance cm^{-1}).

containing 3-5 M perchloric acid change rapidly and after 1 day become identical with that of Co^{2+} ion, which may form by the stepwise dissociation of both 'biguanide' chelates and ultimate decomposition of the resulting tetraaquo complex. In the present investigation only the dissociation of the first chelate is reported. Kinetic runs were carried out in stoppered Jena volumetric flasks placed in a thermostat where the temperature was held to within $\pm 0.1^\circ$ of the desired value. At suitable intervals, 2 ml portions of the solutions were withdrawn and quenched by putting in a pyrex glass test tube placed in ice and absorbance measurements were made in one cm stoppered quartz cells after raising the temperature to room temperature. The rate of aquation of the complex in acid medium was measured in an excess of the reagent such that the first order rate law was applicable. Ionic strength was maintained with required amount of sodium perchlorate. Measurements were carried out at 410 nm, where the difference between the absorption of the complex and its reaction products is maximum. The pseudo first order rate constants were evaluated graphically by plotting $\log(A_0 - A_\infty)/(A_t - A_\infty)$ against 'time' where A_0 , A_t and A_∞ represent, absorbance at start, time 't' and at the end of the reaction respectively.

Identification of the dissociation products :

500 ml of a 0.005 M solution of the complex in 0.2 M perchloric acid was kept at room temperature for 48 hours. It was then dried up completely in a rotary evaporator and taken with *ca.* 20 ml of water and allowed to crystallize in air. Small orange-yellow crystals of $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_7)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{CN})_2] \text{ClO}_4$ appeared in 3-4 days along with white prismatic crystals of biguanide perchlorate. These orange-yellow crystals were separated by hand picking and recrystallized from water and analysed. Cobaltous ion could not be detected from the solution at this stage by spectrophotometric method⁹.

Instead of perchloric acid, when nitric acid was used in the dissociation study, better yield of the rhombic ruby red crystals of $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_7\text{N}_5)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{CN})_2] \text{NO}_3$ were obtained along with biguanide nitrate.

Analysis : Orange-yellow compound : found-Co. 17.30 ; N. 27.90 ; Cl. 10.43 ; H_2O -10.21 $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_7\text{N}_5)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{CN})_2] \text{ClO}_4$ requires-Co. 16.95 ; N. 28.20 ; Cl. 10.20 ; H_2O -10.34 Ruby-red compound : found-Co. 19.42 ; N. 36.47 ; H_2O -10.30 $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_7\text{N}_5)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{CN})_2] \text{NO}_3$ requires-Co. 19.04 ; N. 36.12 ; H_2O -11.61

Thermogravimetry of the product compounds showed that these compounds did not lose any significant amount of their weight before 180° indicating ' H_2O ' must have been coordinated to metal atom. When the dissociation reaction was carried out at 90° in 3M HClO_4 , within few hours the solution loses its colour with complete dissociation of the complex. The solution was evaporated in a rotary evaporator and Co^{2+} ion and 'biguanide perchlorate' were identified by spectrophotometric method⁹ and copper-biguanide complex formation¹⁰. Cyanide, as HCN , was identified by blowing air successively through the experimental solution and small amount of dil. sodium hydroxide solution throughout the experimental run, and then identifying CN^- in this NaOH solution by the usual procedure.

Results and Discussion

The values of the pseudo first order rate constants for the dissociation of the complex at 28° and $\mu=0.5$ but different concentrations of perchloric acid are given in Table 1. The observed rate of dissociation is same for different amounts of complex ion, so the rate is first order dependent on complex concentration. A plot of k_{obs} vs $[\text{H}^+]$ (Fig. 2) gives a straight line passing through origin indicating that the rate is also first order with respect to H^+ ion.

Fig. 2. Effect of acid (HClO_4) concentration on the rate of dissociation at a particular temperature (28°) μ , 0.5.

TABLE—1 EFFECT OF ACID CONCENTRATION ON THE DISSOCIATION OF *trans*-DICYANOBISBIGUANIDECOBALT(III) ION. $\mu = 0.5$; TEMP. 28°.

Complex $\times 10^{-3}$ M	0.5	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.5
HClO ₄ , M	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.5
10 ⁶ k sec ⁻¹	2.19	4.50	4.68	7.18	12.0

The dissociation of the complex in acid medium may be represented by the overall equation of the following type.

where 'BH' stands for a molecule of biguanide. This reaction occurs through the formation of a protonated intermediate as in the case of other biguanide complexes¹, where the rate of dissociation runs parallel to the basicity of the ligand.

Dissociation of the *trans*-dicyanobisethylenediamine complex ion in presence of 1-5 M perchloric acid at room temperature and also at 90° was investigated. In this case, as 'en' (=ethylenediamine) do not have any centre for protonation¹, no protonated intermediate formation takes place which can initiate an acid-catalyzed dissociation. Consequently the reaction rate is extremely slow, and the complex is perfectly inert in this condition. No observable change was noticed in the course of seven days.

The effect of ionic strength on the rate of dissociation of complex ion is given in Table 2. Rate

 TABLE—2 EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH ON THE DISSOCIATION OF *trans*-DICYANOBISBIGUANIDECOBALT(III) CHLORIDE

Complex	5 $\times 10^{-4}$ M	HClO ₄ -0.2 M	Temp. 28°
' μ ' M	0.2 0.3	0.4	0.5
10 ⁶ K sec ⁻¹	2.43 2.63	3.37	4.68

increases with ionic concentration. No account could be made for this observation. Activation parameters, ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger were evaluated by making use of Eyring¹¹ equation of the form

$$\log \frac{kh}{kT} = \frac{\Delta S^\ddagger}{2.303 R} - \frac{\Delta H^\ddagger}{2.303 RT} + \log [\text{HClO}_4].$$

where h, k and R have their usual significance

(Fig. 3). The observed values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger are 15.6 ± 1.2 kcal mol⁻¹ and -24 ± 3 e.u.

A comparison of the ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger values obtained in this case along with the acid-catalyzed

 Fig. 3. Eyring plot for the dissociation of *trans*dicyanobisbiguanidecobalt(III) ion.

dissociation of *tris*-biguanidecobalt(III) ion and diaquo-*bis*-biguanidecobalt(III) ion (Table 3) indicates that similar mechanism operates in all the three cases.

TABLE—3 ACTIVATION PARAMETERS AND RATE OF DISSOCIATION OF SOME COBALT(III)-BIGUANIDE COMPLEXES

Complex	k _{obs} , sec ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	Ref.
	HClO ₄ -0.5 M $\mu = 1$ M, 40°	kcal/mol	e.u.	
Co(BigH) ₃ ³⁺	1.36×10^{-3} (extrapolated value)	11.1	-31.5	1
<i>cis</i> -Co(BigH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ ²⁺	9.5×10^{-6} (extrapolated value)	15.2	-31.6	12
<i>trans</i> -Co(BigH) ₂ (CN) ₂ ⁺	6.3×10^{-4}	15.6	-24.0	This work

In this complex, the electron donation by cyanide to the metal atom, is partly taken back through π -bond, leaving the metal atom apparently more positive than in *tris*-biguanide complex. Thus cobalt atom acquires better acceptor properties for electrons and the metal-ligand (biguanide) bonds become stronger. Consequently greater energy (ΔH^\ddagger) is required for the rupture of the bond as observed in this case. The ΔH^\ddagger values for this complex and that of Co(BigH)₂(H₂O)₂²⁺ are equal, showing metal-ligand bonds are of equal strength, but the reduced cationic, charge of this complex favours the formation of the intermediate more than that with the diaquo-complex with positively charged proton, and the aquation rate becomes higher. The electron withdrawal by *trans*-cyanide ions, lowers the electron density around cobalt atom equally in all directions and the bond formation by the incoming 'water molecule' is not favoured until and unless the departure of the 'biguanide' takes place. So, "bond breaking" is the only important factor in the transition state.

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